

The Diocesan Finance Council [C.492 and C.493]

Roque Alphonso

The Diocesan Finance Council or Committee is an obligatory body in every diocese. Every juridical person has to have a Finance committee. Once the diocese is established, it is the duty of the first Diocesan Bishop to establish the Finance committee along with other obligatory bodies such as the priests' council, consulters' etc. It is to be composed of at least three of Christ's faithful. It has both consultative and deliberative voice.

Persons who are related to the Diocesan bishop in affinity or up to the fourth degree of consanguinity cannot be members of the Finance Committee because of the possibility of "Nepotism." In this council, there are no ex officio members but the Diocesan bishop may include, the vicar general, the chancellor, an expert in canon law, laity, both women and men, who are experts in civil law like CA, Bank officer or bank manager, working in finances etc. The members need to take the oath of honesty and confidentiality. The members of the finance committee are appointed for five years.

Their main function is to take care of the Temporal Goods of the Diocese as per the Book V of the Code of the Canon law. The finance council is responsible for preparing each year a budget of income and expenditure and presenting it to the bishop. The committee needs to monitor the financial administrator's implementation of its provisions and policies. It is their duty to do an 'internal audit.' It includes scrutinizing, reviewing and evaluating the already audited annual statements of accounts of the diocese and all the diocesan institutions such as parishes, schools, homes for children, hospitals etc. They can also help to prepare the annual financial report to be sent to the Dicastery for the evangelization of people.

Under the guidance of the Diocesan bishop, they are responsible for the maintenance and protection of the temporal goods. These temporal goods

are used mainly for divine worship, the provision of fitting support for the clergy, and charity, especially for the needy.

About the Author

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THE FINANCE COUNCIL AND THE FINANCE OFFICER

Can. 492 §1. In every diocese a Finance council is to be established, over which the diocesan bishop himself or his delegate presides and which consists of at least three members of the Christian faithful truly expert in Financial affairs and civil law, outstanding in integrity, and appointed by the bishop.

§2. Members of the Finance council are to be appointed for Five years, but at the end of this period they can be appointed for other Five year terms.

§3. Persons who are related to the bishop up to the fourth degree of consanguinity or affinity are excluded from the Finance council.

Can. 493 In addition to the functions entrusted to it in Book V, The Temporal Goods of the Church, the Finance council prepares each year, according to the directions of the diocesan bishop, a budget of the income and expenditures which are foreseen for the entire governance of the diocese in the coming year and at the end of the year examines an account of the revenues and expenses.